

Start

Fertilization and division

End Reproduction!

Game of the Clam

The objective of the game is to reach space 36, which corresponds to the reproduction stage, the ultimate goal of the species. Along the way, players will find out the life stages of the clam: "Veliger Larva," "Juvenile Clam," and "Adult Clam." The number of spaces between these stages reflects the duration of each phase. On the board, there are green and red spaces representing potential favourable events and unfavourable/hazardous conditions that may occur throughout these animals' life.

Game start: All players roll the dice and the player with the highest number will start as first. The pieces start from space 1, which corresponds to the "trochophore" developmental stage.

Game play: Movement of the pieces along the path is determined by rolling the dice, with the pieces advancing the number of spaces indicated by the dice. When a piece lands on a space, it must follow the instructions related to that space. The winner is the first player that reaches the space 36.

The Good Spaces

Space 11: Chlorophyll: Gnam! So good! Do 3 spaces more.

Space 12 & 24: Priming: You will be resistant to heatwaves and chemical contamination (space 13-15-22-27). You can use this benefit only one time.

Space 26: Symbionts: Thank you friends! Go to the space number 28.

Space 33: Chlorophyll: Gnam! So good! Do 3 spaces more.

The Hazard Spaces

Space 5: Storm surge: The storm brought you too far... Back to the start.

Space 8: Water acidification: your shell is too thin to be resistant... Go back to space number 2.

Space 10: *Bolinus brandaris*: oh no! a murex holed your shell and ate you! Back to the start.

Space 13: Chemical contamination: it's not good for your health. Go back to space number 9.

Space 15: Heatwaves: Ops! This climate change is affecting you. Go 1 space back.

Space 17: Blue crab: oh no! a blue crab ate you! Back to the start!

Space 20: Temperature increasing: Too warm! Stop here for a turn and try to adapt.

Space 22: Chemical contamination: It's not good for your health. Go back to space number 8.

Space 27: Heatwaves: Ops! This climate change is affecting you. Go 3 spaces back.

Space 31: Pathogens: They are not friends... Try to fight them: roll the dice again.

If you get N° 1-2-3: you are too weak. Skip a turn. N° 4-5-6 Great! You are safe!

Space 34: Plastic pollution: you filtered microplastics! Stop for a turn until you excrete them (if you can!). Roll the dice. N° 1-2-3 skip a turn; N° 4-5-6 you are safe!

Space 35: Brown Ring Disease: Nooo! There is *Vibrio tapetis*! Go back 5 spaces.

